

Design and implementation of Multistage Linear Feedback Shift Register Counters with low hardware complexity

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Abstract: A well-suited application in the Wide Array counter, the Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) Counter may boost the circuit's efficiency in terms of space and performance, in comparison to the standard binary counter. Consequently, a substantial amount of logic, resulting in an increase in area, is necessary to convert the pseudorandom pattern order of the LFSR series into binary representation. Using the suggested sequence-logic LFSR counter in conjunction with binary counters, this article presents a multi-stage LFSR counter design. The old counter had little effect on latency or power, but merging the two would have made a better performance and area presentation. A multi-stage LFSR counter with a four-bit pattern generator is integrated into this design with the help of Xilinx 14.7.

Keywords: Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR), decoding logic, binary counters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital circuits often use shift registers, a kind of sequential logic circuit, to store digital data in a linear fashion with inputs linked to outputs in such a manner that the data is sent down the line upon circuit activation.

If a shift register's output is a linear function of two greater than its previous states (taps), then the input bit of that register is called a linear feedback shift register. Every one of the m phases that make up an LFSR may store one bit of data; the phases are numbered 0, 1, 2, ..., $m-1$.

to regulate the flow of data. One of the first things an LFSR needs is the seed. Because there is a limited number of potential states for each given register, periodicity is an inevitable consequence. If the feedback function and seed are carefully selected, an LFSR may produce a long-lived sequence of bits that seems random (and has acceptable statistical features).

While LFSRs are more often seen in pseudorandom number generators, they have also shown to be a reliable source for synchronous counters. The shift register's ability to function as a serial reading device makes them ideal for use in wide array implementations. LFSR counters have been integrated into single-photon detector arrays and the pixel architecture of Complementary Metal Oxide semiconductors. The amount of bits in the counter has no effect on the clock speed of the LFSR, and all states in the state space are traversed except for the zero states. Having said that, linear feedback shift registers use pseudo-random counting, therefore

To convert the LFSR series to binary order, more processing is required.

Three distinct approaches use the decrypted binary patterns from the LFSR sequence:

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the Lookup Table 3. A method for balancing the use of time and memory. For system-on-chip designs to implement this decoding on the chip, it is crucial to decode each cell in the array in binary order, which is necessary for wide array applications. This stipulation verifies that the decoding logic must be integrated and quick because of the need of many conversions. In addition, expanding the LFSR in terms of either time or field causes all of the previously described approaches to improve in a consistent manner. Certain examples of arrayed structures cannot be implemented with LFSR counters unless very large integrated LUTs are developed for use in single-photon detection.

Fig. 1 Block diagram of the multistage LFSR counter.

Logic that grows logarithmically, not exponentially, with counter size may be used to interpret the modern counter design that is described in this paper, which is the consequence of many LFSR phases. In contrast to the drastic performance drop that would result from just adding more LFSR counters—which are essentially binary ripple counters—this research offers a method to space out the ripple signal and a less complicated framework for logic decoding.

II. EXISTING METHOD

One may see the counter-architecture schematic. M activated signal-controlled n -LFSR comparable blocks have been implemented. Once the activation signal is confirmed, m th n -LFSR will advance one state if $(m-1)$ th n -LFSR encounters a certain state change. The whole $M*n$ bit state space may therefore be traversed. In big array designs, the counter may also function as a high-speed serial readout chain, avoiding the ripple carrying and LFSR feedback loops with almost no extra circuitry. The LFSR counter structure makes the counter into M independent modules, which means that the $n*n$ bit LUT may decode each n -LFSR independently, instead of using the $(Mn) \times (Mn)$ bit LUT. A small n allows us to implement LUT on a chip.

Fig. 2 (a) Configuration of a standard n -bit ring generator. (b) Configuration of standard many-to-one 4-LFSRs.

Since these missing LFSR series states would lead the counter state space to miss out on huge chunks of counter states, every counter stage is triggered within a single cycle of the preceding step. Consequently, the n -LFSR must be prepared for a most time allowed. A missing state must be included into the count sequence using extra circuitry since the sequence length of an n -max LFSR is only $2n - 1$. This

is accomplished when the feedback logic is disabled by setting both the NOR and XOR procedures to 0x000. This pattern-extension logic increases the pattern length of the individual LFSR sections to $2n$, allowing the counter to maintain any state in the $2Mn$ state space. Another area where the multi-stage counter shines is in self-starting counters and other applications requiring coverage for any state, where conventional LFSRs just won't cut it. The LFSR feedback and ripple-carry blocks are bypassed by using rather simple logic. A multi-stage counter method reduces the counter to Min-dependent parts, allowing for the independent decipherment of each n-LFSR using an n-bit LUT rather than a $(M*n)*(M*n)$ bit LUT. For small n , the LUT may be simply integrated into the semiconductor.

Fig.3 Block diagram of a proposed n-LFSR multi-stage block with logic for sequence-extension (dotted components). The complete feedback block is realized as a single logic block.

Fig. 4. Timing diagram of the multistage LFSR counter operation. Arrows illustrate the operation of the logic of the ripple-carry. Further processing by the decoding logic includes highlighted states.

Ripple-Carry Logic:

Given that the n-LFSR stores all of the states in the state space, it is imperative that the LFSR provide the shift to 0b1111 0b0111. As this migration happens in every n-LFSR design, it is a good fit for the ripple's trigger state, which is a Gray-code transition. The starting point of the n-LFSR pattern is now set to 0b0111. After then, 0 x..00..00 is the result of decrypting the encoding logic. In order for a LUT to accurately decode each stage in a single clock cycle—a design goal of the counter—the ripple signal must go through each stage and determine whether or not it is going to migrate. On the other hand, the ripple signal is only applied to the stage immediately after it; this way, the output of the counter is kept from decreasing when more stages are added, and the ripple signal is brought for the steps that follow until the next clock cycle. Additionally, it gives the mth process's clock cycle delay to the transition edge and the transition edge over time.

How the ripple-carry logic works is shown by the counter-timing sketch. Each LFSR state is represented by a binary number (0b), in contrast to the LUT (LUT)

The deciphered state seems to be the same hex value (0x...) for all other states (decipher signal). A RIPPLE 0 signal is generated when LFSR 0 changes from the 0b1111... State to the 0b0111... State. On the subsequent clock edge, the RIPPLE 0 signal may likewise go through the 0b1111... 0b0111... transition since it works on LFSR 1. On the flip side, this causes LFSR 2 to operate by means of a ripple signal on the subsequent clock edge. In this way, the ripple-carry logic

permits the transformation's edge to be postponed. In

addition to the $n \times n$ -bit LUT with a little amount of decoding logic, those states that the LUT incorrectly deciphered must be rectified.

Decoding Logic:

As a post-processing step, decoding logic affects the performance of the multi-stage LFSR counter array. This is because LUT is used to send every value from the list that is read from the Linear Feedback Shift Register. The LUT transforms the majority of states into a binary format. Therefore, suitable reasoning is required to fix the mistakes caused by the postponed changeover.

Look Up Table encoding errors may be classified into two categories. Initial faults as well as overflow faults. Any time the counter reaches a condition at the top of the transition fault triangle before the m th phase transition, it is considered an initial fault in the clock cycle. Each stage's deciphered value is equal to the number of clock cycles after the start of the transition edge. These mistakes might be identified until the decoded value of the subsequent stages is identical to $m-1$, as the ripple takes m clock cycles to reach the m th process. When an error occurs early enough to be equivalent to $0x.FF.FF$, it is called an overflow error. Such errors could indicate that a ripple event occurred on a prior clock cycle, perhaps induced by a stage that came before it. An overflow error and $0x...FF$ will be shown in the following step if the current stage is faulty. If you execute the increase with the next point invalid registry, you will be able to identify it. It is possible to identify first mistakes by comparing the previously decoded phases stored in latches with the counter that records the current phase number. If this stage is different from the one before it, an error will be introduced into the next step.

deciphered amount. In order for the counter to reach M , it needs bits from the set $y = \lceil \log_2(M) \rceil$ to count. This means that the only y -bit connection that has to be formed is between the ones that have already been decoded.

Fig. 5. Logic to decode the order of the multistage LFSR counter state into binary. Each stage is decoded in sequence.

The time required to interpret the count value is dependent on n and M . In order to decode the maximum count value, M clock cycles are needed, as decoding logic takes one clock cycle per counter point. There is an implementation-dependent but theoretically important approach to decoding logic that involves the LUT, incrementer, and comparison to the stage counter; however, the efficiency of these components decreases for big n .

III. PROPOSED METHOD

We suggest a multi-stage counter design that makes use of binary counters and linear feedback shift register counters. When compared to the original, the combined performance of these two counters is much improved. The suggested four-stage counter architecture is comprised of binary counters and linear feedback shift registers in the first step. By using linear feed shift registers where needed and binary counters as optional, performance may be improved over the prior setup. Logic based on ripples (RCL) makes use of the whole bit stream and the result values of the right counter. There are two counters that use ripple carry logic to keep data deterioration to a minimum. Additionally, Ripple Carry Logic is crucial due to

its counter implementation. See picture 6 for an illustration of the counter.

Fig. 6 Proposed architecture multistage LFSR counter design

All of the counter's outputs in a multistage design are pseudo-random. For single photon applications, the conversion of LFSR pseudo random counting to binary counting is crucial. Logic Interpretation was the tool that got the job done here. The existing multi-stage counter employs the same decoding mechanism as this suggested counter. When converting LFSR count values to binary form, this decoding logic uses fewer comparisons than earlier decoding algorithms. Using binary counters for subsequent stages and the Linear Feedback Shift Register counter only for the first stage leads to great performance in the proposed multi-stage counter implementation.

Binary Counter:

Many digital apps make use of counters to keep track of various actions. A sequential circuit is a counter. An electronic circuit that counts

a counter is what pulses are called. Of all the flip-flop applications, the Counter is by far the most common. A clock signal is applied to a set of flip-flops. Two types of counters

are available. 1. Ripples, which are unsynchronized counters. Synchronous counters are the second kind. The counting method determines whether the counters are synchronous or asynchronous. Rising counters The counters that go up and down. Counts that go up and down. As a kind of memory that stores one bit of state, flip-flops or latches are essential components in digital circuitry. Digital state machines may be built utilising many flip-flops. A binary counter, which merely cycles through its states, is essentially a state machine that operates on each step of a clock signal. Since different types of flip-flops handle feedback differently to the J and K terminals, the JK configuration—widely recognised as the most universal—can be used. Here, the usage of flip-flops for a toggling function implies that the output is changed with each finished clock cycle. The flip-flops are connected to the J and K pins in order to do this. By leaving the J and K terminals set to zero, the output will never change independently of the input. The signal to link the J and K terminals in the circuit is perfect because of this.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In contrast to the current design, the suggested one prioritises hardware efficiency without sacrificing any of the other criteria. The suggested and current multi-stage counter designs have all been functionally tested using the 14.7 version of Xilinx. Because we are using binary counters, the suggested process will have a smaller footprint, which will enhance the efficiency of the design.

Fig.7 RTL Schematic of proposed Multistage counter

Fig.8 Technology Schematic of proposed Multistage counter

Fig.9 Simulation output of Proposed Multistage counter

Table:1 Evaluation of Area, Delay and Power report

	Area	Delay	Power
Existing	23	5.406ns	0.034w
Proposed	20	5.406ns	0.034w

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a hardware-efficient design for multi-stage counter implementation, along with the decoding logic needed to transform the series of random counts into binary form. This is necessary because applications do not directly utilise the pseudo-random format generated by linear feedback shift registers. To improve the area efficiency, this work introduces a Multistage LFSR counter needs that combines LFSR with binary counters. The previous multi-stage counter, which relied only on linear feedback shift registers throughout, and the proposed one, which employs binary counters in the second stage, have both been functionally confirmed using the 14.7 version of Xilinx. Findings demonstrate that the suggested layout uses less space than the current system while keeping energy and latency constant.

REFERENCES

[1] N. Mukherjee, J. Rajski, G. Mrugalski, A. Pogiel, and J. Tyszer, "Ring generator: An ultimate linear feedback shift register," *IEEE Comput.*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 64–71, Jun. 2011.

[2] D. Bronzi, F. Villa, S. Tisa, A. Tosi, and F. Zappa, "SPAD figures of merit for photon-counting, photon-timing, and imaging applications: A review," *IEEE Sensors J.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 3–12, Jan. 2016.

[3] V. Friedman and S. Liu, "Dynamic logic CMOS circuits," *IEEE J. Solid- State Circuits*, vol. JSSC-19, no. 2, pp. 263–266, Apr. 1984.

- [4] Alfke, P, Efficient shift registers, LFSR counters, and long pseudorandom sequence generators, Xilinx Inc., San Jose, CA, USA, Tech. Rep. XAPP 052, Jul. 1996.
- [5] Boudinov, H, et al. Quaternary look-up tables using voltage-mode CMOS logic design, in Proc. 37th Int. Symp. Multiple- Valued Logic (ISMVL), 2007, p. 56.
- [6] C. Yoo, A CMOS buffer without short-circuit power consumption, IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. II, Analog Digit. Signal Process., vol. 47, no. 9, pp.935–937, Sep. 2000.
- [7] L. Ding and P. Mazumder, “On circuit techniques to improve noise immunity of CMOS dynamic logic,” IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst., vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 910–925, Sep. 2004.
- [8] Palumbo, G, et al. Understanding the effect of process variations on the delay of static and domino logic, IEEE Trans. Very Large Scale Integr. (VLSI) Syst., vol. 18, no. 5, pp. 697–710, May 2010.
- [9] D. W. Clark and L.-J. Weng, Maximal and near-maximal shift register sequences: Efficient event counters and easy discrete logarithms, IEEE Trans. Comput., vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 560–568, May 1994.
- [10] N. Mukherjee, A. Pogiel, J. Rajski, and J. Tyszer, “High-speed on-chip event counters for embedded systems,” in Proc. 22nd Int. Conf. VLSI Design, 2009, pp. 275–280.
- [11] T. A. Abbas, N. A. W. Dutton, O. Almer, N. Finlayson, F. M. D. Rocca, and R. Henderson, A CMOS SPAD sensor with a multievent folded flash time-to-digital converter for ultra-fast optical transient capture, IEEE Sensors J., vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 3163–3173, Apr. 2018.
- [12] Boisvert, A, et al. Low dead time digital SPAD readout architecture for realtime small animal PET,” in Proc. IEEE Nucl. Sci. Symp. Med. Imag. Conf. (NSS/MIC), Oct. 2013, pp. 1–6.
- [13] Krstajic, N et al. A 256×8 SPAD line sensor for time resolved fluorescence and raman sensing, in Proc. 40th Eur. Solid-State Circuits Conf. (ESSCIRC), 2014, pp. 143–146.